

STRATEGIC ELEMENTS OF POST-PANDEMIC DEVELOPMENT OF THE ROMANIAN MOUNTAIN AGRITURISM

Romulus GRUIA, Liviu GACEU

Universitatea Transilvania din Braşov, ecotec@unitbv.ro

Abstract

*In the present historical, climate and economic conditions, it becomes more than necessary that in the **National Agri-food Strategy** to be achieved new directions regarding adaptation after COVID-19 pandemic. The paper highlights the necessity to study the direction of **special quality** agri-food production from small and medium units in context of ideational and managerial integration concerning the interconnection between agriculture, food, tourism and environment. In this interpenetration zone, agritourism becomes an element where life quality and health interpenetrate with food quality and hygienic-sanitary safety. The paper orders ideas and concludes that, following post-pandemic changes, the combination „agriculture - tourism” has as necessary to elaborate a concrete strategy so that, through agri-rural tourism, to practically achieve the salvation and maintenance of agricultural exploitations, especially in fragile zones such as the mountainous ones. To renew the strategic model imposes to optimize quality elements generated by the new post-pandemic conditions, with effect that leads to a governance of the mountain resorts with integration and imposing hygienic-sanitary rules with no exception (even after anti-covid vaccination).*

Key words: agritourism, food, mountain, pandemic, strategy.

INTRODUCTION

It is known that the development strategy for every domain is part of a new general „picture”, i.e. the reference elements of a national strategy. In the present case we refer to strategic aspects regarding the branch of agri-rural tourism, with its pragmatic domain of agritourism, taking as reference the situation that has existed in recent decades [COOPER at al, 1998; OMT, 1995; IONAŞCU, Gh., 1995; NISTOREANU, P., 1999; GRUIA, R., 2013, 2015, 2021], as basis for the new orientations for the future.

The agri-rural tourism has the potential to become a viable, stable certitude, presenting itself as a complex well-articulated activity, that will efficiently respond to legitimate needs of economic, social, cultural, spiritual order and that have the possibility to range themselves to the European space. More than that, by the Romanian agri-rural tourism there are created the conditions to keep and conserve the state structural, cultural and spiritual identity, this one being also one of the conditions expressed in the plan of European adherence [BRAN FLORINA, 1997].

For the mountain zones, within these premises, we remind that Romania (together with the Czech Republic, Poland, Ukraine, Hungary, Serbia and Slovakia) is part in the program elaborated in 2014 under the name „*Strategy for Sustainable Development of the Tourism in the Carpathian Mountains*” [UNEP, 2014]. The program goes on under the auspices of the **Framework convention regarding the durable protection and development of the Carpathians (Carpatica Convention)** that, at its turn is administrated by the *Program for Environment of the United Nations* – i.e. a second Sub-region treaty from the world concerning a **border mountain region**.

In the mountain agritourist field, the development of medium farms and of the section of production processing is achieved either at farm level (if the production is high enough), or

at the level of zonal associations, as for example on mountain basins, or cooperatives for several localities. For smaller units, such as usually the mountainous agritourist ones are, a certain strategy is necessary, in order to encourage processing at farm level, respectively in small butcheries, dairies etc. [GRUIA, R., and others, 2015, 2016]. Such a manner to develop the activity is imposed in the idea to capitalize the “mountain product” through tourism. We are revering of course to gastro tourism, namely to culinary processing and serving tourists from the own pension, but also to sale in stores with as original as possible products of the local community [KOSOSSEY, M. ȘI MAJONCHI, D., 1990; STANCIULESCU GABRIELA, 1998; RONDELLI VIORICA, COJOCARU STELIANA, 2005; GRUIA, R, and others, 2018].

As a principle, linked to the development strategy of agri-tourism in general and of the mountain one in special, different programs address the following issues [FRAISSE H., 1990; KOTLER PH., ARMSTRONG G., SAUNDERS J., WONG V., 1999; NISTOREANU P., TUDORESCU N., 2002]:

- **Increasing competitiveness** in agricultural and forestry sectors (to improve knowledge, consolidate the human potential, restructure and develop physical capital);
- **Improving the environment** and the rural space (sustainable use of agricultural and forestry fields);
- **Life quality** in rural zone and diversification of rural economy (diversification of rural economy, especially on direction of capitalizing the agricultural production by food processing and by tourism).

In the sense of those mentioned, the newness of our demarche aims the fact that today reality has deeply changed with COVID-19 pandemic, being especially affected, as it is known, the Tourism Industry and, implicitly, MOUNTAIN AGROTOURISM too. Consequently, the elaboration of a development strategy of mountainous agritourism adapted to the post-pandemic specific situation is required.

The objectives of the paper propose to enlighten certain scientific elements regarding the ideas of **adaptation** of the development of COVID-19 post pandemic agritourism, necessary to elaborate strategic directions of agritourism development from the Carpathian Mountains area and to find solutions of convergence of the mountain agritourism activity between technical-economic and managerial elements, the analyses of the development factors that refer to integration and dosing complementary to the production issue (and adequate marketing), to innovative management and montanological educational process, as well as to the optimization of quality elements generated by the new post-pandemic conditions.

WORKING METHOD

There have been used documentary techniques, of analysis of framework documents (judicial and technical ones) of international and national organizations in the field of mountain tourism. The applied methodology presupposes to collect, systematize and process information, using statistic and managerial methods, as well as a series of a comparative analyses regarding the situation of the Romanian mountain agritourism, before and after the COVID-19 pandemic.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

In post pandemic economic, climate and sanitary conditions it becomes more than necessary that, in the **National agritourist strategy** to concretely achieve a divisions of the activity in two large directions:

- **The direction of the industrial agri-food production** (on the quality principle) with emphasis in the plain area and the peri urban ones;

- **The direction of agri-food production in small and especially medium units** (on the quality principle) in relation with the specific *geo-pedo-climate* conditions: for fragile zones (mountain, pre-mountain, wet zones) and the deep plain and hill ones without infrastructure.

Deepening the direction of agri-food production of special QUALITY from small and medium units, we get to the special situation of **interconnection between agriculture, diet, tourism and environment**. This interpenetration zone that constitutes the field of the **Responsible Tourism** (where we also find agritourism) presupposes at its turn an objective structure, in conformity with the perceived reality. In a general acceptance we precise the idea that *responsible tourism* encompasses recreation in rural scenery or natural environment, with participation at or experimentation of activities, events or attraction points that are not available in urban zones. This scenery encompasses natural reserves, open rural zones (pastoral forest), villages and agricultural zones, but also cultural objectives, as well as customs and traditions of the rural zone. In principle, all these are typologically structured in two directions: tourism in natural landscape and agri-rural tourism, with its basic economic component: agritourism (fig.1).

Fig. 1. Components of the polyvalent field of tourism connection with agriculture and both with Nature

In essence, the relation *tourism-agriculture* constitutes a modality of local development that, as a scientific demarche, is the expression of professional preoccupations of experts in territorial development or landscape management, unfortunately almost-non-existent scientific demarche in our country. That is why experts in public food and agritourism have the opportunity and even the obligation to replace this lack. In this context, adjacent acquired competences make possible the objective and of high professionalism understanding of the relation „*agriculture - tourism*”. The nuances of this relation still need many studies, especially if in the „equation” we are also referring to fragile zones, such as the mountain ones are.

In the context of those mentioned, there may be enumerated several programs and basic actions in tourism industry, among which there are to be also found elements linked to

agritourist evolution [GLĂVAN, V., 2003]. Thus, agritourist development may be complementary to the improvement of capitalization at superior level of the mountain tourism that is not yet capitalized in Romania in conformity with the existing potential. One of the examples may be that one concerning the diversification of investment types and construction of new objectives with double functionality (winter sports and recreation), with capitalization of the zone tourist market such as for example the one from the Apuseni Mountains. Generalizing, we consider the relation between mountain agritourism and the extension of the offer to practice winter sports and modernization of the main mountain tourist resorts of international interest (Sinaia, Predeal, Poiana Braşov) as having a synergic effect for a mountain massif. The effect would be the increasing interest for the tourist application in mountain resorts, and some of the mountain tourist villages might become tourist resorts.

Policies and forecast in the future evolution of the mountain agritourism

It is necessary to develop more **products / tourist programs** that should NOT refer to accommodation, but especially in order to improve *the range of attractions and activities* offered to visitors. Especially, on the basis of the concept of *sustainable development*, there are **opportunities** to expand the visitors 'activities in the protected zones. The result will be a significantly positive impact on local community's providers, from inside or protected zones surroundings. A larger publicity of the rural traditional events is necessary, in order to facilitate the visitors 'planning. On the other hand, it is recommended that **natural reservations** make plans of sustainable development of the tourism after the „*Retezat*” model and look for financing for identified facilities for the visitors.

New policies in tourism and, even more, in agritourism, which is so deeply anchored in economic realities, are expressed after conducting economic and social assessments. These ones enlighten tourism effects and express **future opportunities**:

- type of tourist development, that may have a positive or negative character in its relation with agriculture;
- the fact that favorable results don't appear automatically, but must be searched and established;
- the interest to look for an increase of tourism economic results through different actions (trade, increasing seasonality, increase of tourist investments, complex tourist product making);
- necessity to accompany the development effort by an effort of organization and concentration of all local efforts.

It is desirable the issue in Romania as well of a program of university studies that may train development specialists, as there is already one in certain countries with tradition. As well as it is desirable that institutions in tourism industry, especially administrative ones (example ONT), give priority to public relations and promotional assistance to different **rural associations**. And this especially because the range of products and activities that this one is encouraging represents one of the most important values of Romania's brand image. The network proposed by *regional development inspectors* will support individual rural providers with guidance regarding development within a larger regional and national context. Also, they will facilitate to create structures, as local promotional consortiums are. At the same time, inspectors will facilitate data collecting regarding events, points of attraction and activities through the local network of the *Tourist Information Centers (TIC)*, in order to include relevant promotional activities in the data base of the national tourism too.

Tourism in mountain rural zones becomes more and more attractive, as tourists become more mobile and look for a change to city life. But the way they penetrate and understand life in the country differs from a visitor to another. Certain visitors wish to be mere spectators. Others wish to directly get involved in projects of environmental protection and conservation or in agricultural activities specific to mountain zones.

Therefore there are *development provocations* and *promotional provocations* that must be solved if potential visitors are offered and informed with the corresponding products.

From organizational perspective, in recent years there has been a significant both quantitative and qualitative increase of rural accommodation units due to individual investors and SAPARD financing, especially on direction of agritourism. The activity of certain organizations, such as *ANTREC*, supports rural providers to enter the market. At the same time, organizations such as *ADEPT* and *The Ecotourism Association* help rural communities to appreciate the meaning of tourism and understand what advantages they may get from tourism.

Non-governmental associations, as well as governmental policy may also induce another strategic aspect, namely the formation of **local cooperatives with rural tourism products** – *healthy food, attractions, accommodation and retail activities* –, necessary strategy to attract visitors 'attention on certain zones of the country.

New orientations in European policies of development of agritourism

It seems paradoxical, but Covid-19 pandemic may also be considered an **opportunity of modernization** of all tourism industry structures, making it more ecological and more responsible from social point of view. In Romania, due to natural and cultural inheritance kept unaltered on extended areas, the Carpathian Mountains are a top tourist destination in Europa (fig.2). As added value for the Carpathian mountain tourism, we mention:

- The inhabitants of the Romanian Carpathian Mountains (still) keep local authentic traditions, the culture and natural landscapes, which contributes to unique tourist experiences;
- In local communities where there is a good cooperation the quality of the responsible mountain tourism (rural tourism, agritourism, ecotourism and others) improves.

Fig. 2 - Tourist destination - the Carpathian Mountains

Strategically, it becomes essential for the development of the mountain zones to interconnect with yield mountain agriculture with mountain tourism. On this basis there practically take shape several essential orientations in the relation tourism-agriculture [Bran Florina, and others 1997], that may constitute the basis to make a **plan of development policy** and information for the arrangement of the mountain territory (table 1).

Table 1
Strategic relation „tourism - agriculture”

No.	TYPE OF RELATION	CHARACTERISTICS OF THE RELATION
1	In the formation and education of the potential tourists concerning possible consequences that their presence and behavior may have upon their agricultural activities:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - making explanatory documents (flyers, brochures, guides), that have the role of “good behavior codes” and a well done dissemination system; - organization of manifestations, as well as “Open farms days”, where tourists, especially schoolchildren and students may better know the realities of rural world.
2	Choice of the best solutions in using the rural space for tourist purposes:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - making documentation of zoning of the territory, especially in zones with maximum tourist pressure and establishing priorities of development of the tourism; - elaboration of documents of « agricultural book » type, that refer to regional policies from the Counties, concerning the use of space and the establishment of the right to build in agricultural zones, in imposing regulations for tourism.
3	Promotion of forms of tourism with the least impact upon agriculture:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - carrying out tourist activities, such as: accommodation at citizens (rooms for rent, guest rooms, camping in the farm), holiday villages; - establishing rigorous principles of organization and development of the infrastructure (proportionality, functionality, esthetics, ambiance etc.).
4	Making projects or solutions based on the concept of complementarity of activities:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - construction of polyvalent equipment (for ex., making anthropic aquatic accumulations with double utilization, agricultural and touring); - utilization of associated arrangement methods with agritourist valences. <p>[N.B.- Thus, there may be proposed lands for constructions in exchange of agricultural ones, for those who wish to build, which implies actions of commune promotion, both for agricultural activities and tourist ones].</p>
5	Including tourist projects in a global framework:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - from this point of view it is necessary to be integrated in a plan of rural arrangement at micro-region level (example of PUG type).

Perspective of development of agritourism in Romania

Strategic principles and directions at international level may be also applied and adapted for our country. In essence, strategies will be based on a „triangle” of factors (fig.3).

Fig. 3. Perspective of development of the mountain agritourism

It is obvious that mountain agritourism can't successfully evolve without the mountain area and local community, without the existence of agritourist units (farms + pensions) and without visitors (mountain lover tourists). These are factors to capitalize local tourist resources and implicitly, to raise the standard of living of the respective village inhabitants. Thus, the idea of socio-economic development of the rural locality and of the community in general may be consolidated, in the context of protecting and conserving the natural and built environment of the mountain zones.

Therefore, **the rural tourism and agritourism** constitute themselves as an economic-social activity that superiorly valorizes material, spiritual and human resources and benefits of its services and technical-municipal endowment. From here also local authorities' necessity to directly imply in the public policies of the mountain space.

Concretely, strategic application of the policy of revitalization of the Romanian mountain agritourism has as main directions production aspects (*action 1*), the management ones (*action 2*) and of education ones (*action 3*), necessary to the field (table 2).

Table 2

Post-pandemic strategies on the axes „production - management - education” in mountain agritourism

PLAN OF ACTION	NAME	PUNCTUAL STRATEGY DIRECTIONS
Plan 1.	Framework PRODUCTION & MARKETING diagram with	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Creation of a Carpathian identity and initiation of a slogan/logo obligatory for all service providers who their membership to the range of Carpathian agro-food de products - Initiation and creation of a system of certification and labelling for

	<p>emphasis of post-pandemic Covid-19 hygienic-sanitary specificity</p>	<p>sustainable tourism as <i>Carpathian brand</i> for the mountain agritourism</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Development of a standard system of the quality of Carpathian food for local products and services / ex.: „Mountain product” ; <i>Code of behavior in mountain tourism etc.</i> - Elaboration of commune principles and guides regarding mountain tourist infrastructure - Constitution of a cooperation platform of mountain destination tour-operators - Projection of a common marking system specific for agritourist routes from the Carpathians (complementary to standard tourist markings) - Constitution (and updating) of an on-line platform for mountain products made in the mountain agritourist activity - Making publications and maps with agritourist units, with breakdown for each massif of the Carpathian Mountains
<p>Plan 2.</p>	<p>Development of the MANAGERIAL PROCESS in the post – pandemic innovative mountain agri-tourism</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Mobilization of resources in order to implement the Development strategy of the mountain agritourism - Establishment of regulations and award, protection and use mechanisms of the <i>Carpathian brand</i> on massifs, regarding the mountain product - Making a program regarding agritourist resource convergence from every country member of the Carpathian Convention - Elaboration of methodologies and guides regarding mountain agritourism organization necessary to support different public policies in the field, taking into consideration the principles of sustainable development, landscape and biodiversity preservation, but also the socio-economic and cultural impact - Publication of guides for sustaining and applying the sanitary recommendations for mountain product (food or non-food ones) supply and marketing chains - Making a system of monitoring traffic and tourist safety from the Carpathian tourist destinations, in connection to the flow of tourists from the mountain agritourist units
<p>Plan 3.</p>	<p>Renewal of the montanologic EDUCATIONAL PROCESS</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Training courses for medium and superior level as specialization in mountain agritourism (including initiation in writing investment or research-development projects) - Creation of an on-line platform (e-learning) of instruction and dissemination of good practices in the mountain agri-tourism, with emphasis on adapting the post-pandemic activity, both to production, but also to the hospitality field - Development of the systems of information communication and dissemination regarding the mountain agritourism (events, symposiums etc.) - Development of a study program for specialization in the activity from pedagogic mountain farms (school camps, different school etc.) - Mass-media development with a field on mountain media section (making TV and radio talk-shows on mountain tourism, making newspapers, magazines, brochures etc.)

Among the ideas that may be extracted from what has been mentioned in table 2 one may observe the operational remodeling of the mountain agri-tourism in the Carpathians, also based on the new post-pandemic recommendations. There are necessary a series of concrete measures of legal nature, investment in suitable equipment and furniture, technical procedures and punctual sanitary measures.

The result is the possibility to make a *model of post-pandemic strategy in the mountain agritourism from Romania's mountains*. THE RENEWAL OF THE STRATEGIC MODEL imposes the „*bioharmonization*” of the quality elements generated by the new post-pandemic conditions, with effects that lead to a governance of the mountain resorts with integration and imposition at high level of hygienic-sanitary rules (even after the appearance of the anti-covid vaccine), based on 4 basic directions:

- the existence of specific documents, in conformity with post-pandemic recommendations,
- the application of hygienic-sanitary operations,
- the post-pandemic technologic coherence at culinary processing and service
- the ensuring of requirements and recommendations regarding equipment and furniture from the mountain agro tourism pensions.

The new model, in fact a **diffuse tourism with diversified mountain resorts** is based on a series of multiform practices in the idea to underline the identity of the cultural and natural patrimony of the respective territory. It refers to the emphasis of the aspects based on: diversity / on the local socio-economic and administrative network / on intercommunity projects / on models that differ in function of altitude / on adapting to seasonality / on gastro-tourism originality and others. As a general strategy, it is clear that it becomes obligatory to *develop the infrastructure*. Why not, for the decades to come, there may also be aimed the air transportation in the mountain area: small airports, zonal heliports, parking for drone-taxis etc., all of them necessary to get faster to faraway and hard to reach destinations.

CONCLUSIONS

1 - The specificity of the Carpathian mountain agritourism is linked to the *spirit* of the inhabitants of the Romanian Carpathian Mountains, who understand the mountain and (still) keep the local authentic traditions, the culture and preserve the natural landscapes; the result of these aspects is to get mountain products, at the moment on the strategic line of post-pandemic transformations and perfection of hygienic-sanitary measures.

2 - The post-pandemic development of the Romanian mountain agritourism, will take into considerations the basic pillars of the development triangle adapted to anti-pandemic measures, triangle having as references: PEOPLE (mountaineer tourists), MOUNTAIN (the mountain area and local community from the Carpathian area) and AGRITOURIST UNITS from the mountain zones.

3 - The post-pandemic strategy of the mountain agritourism in the Romanian Carpathians has in view *the bioharmonization* of the development factors that refer to integration and dosing complementary to production problem (and appropriate marketing), innovative management and the montanologic educational process.

4 - The renewal of the strategic model imposes to optimize elements linked to quality generated by the new post-pandemic conditions, with effects that lead to a governance of the mountain resorts with integration and imposition with no exception of the hygienic-sanitary rules (even after anti-covid vaccination) and acceleration of the related technical investments.

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